

EASY METHODS OF LEARNING FOREIGN LANGUAGES

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Abstract: This article discusses the increasing demand for learning foreign languages, the most effective and easy ways to learn foreign languages, the role and importance of modern technologies in learning other languages, and what language learners need. It is stated that they should pay attention.

Key words: foreign language, purpose of language learning, grammar, methodology, memory, writing, hearing, communication, modern technology, vocabulary, translation

XORIJIY TILLARNI O'QITISHNING OSON METODLARI

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Annotatsiya: Ushbu maqolada chet tillarini o'rganishga bo'lgan talabning ortishi, chet tillarini o'rganishning eng samarali va oson usullari, boshqa tillarni o'rganishda zamonaviy texnologiyalarning o'rnini va ahamiyati, til o'rganuvchilarga qanday ehtiyoj borligi muhokama qilinadi. ular e'tibor berishlari kerakligi aytilmoqda.

Kalit so'zlar: chet tili, til o'rganish maqsadi, grammatika, metodika, xotira, yozish, gapirish, muloqot, zamonaviy texnologiyalar, lug'at, tarjima chet tillarini o'rganishning oson usullari.

Today, people's knowledge of several foreign languages is considered an important factor for their professional activities, as well as for their personal development. Therefore, one of the requirements of today's time is to know at least one foreign language. As we know, the most spoken languages in the world are English, French, Chinese, Spanish, Russian, Arabic, etc. Learning foreign languages is much easier and more effective using certain proven methods.

Before learning a foreign language, we should clarify our goal, that is, clarifying the goal will help us achieve our goal in the future quickly and easily, according to the plan. If you have decided on your goal and which language to learn, you can choose several methods based on which language learning methods you want to use, your interest and your mastery.

Start learning a language with grammar

There is probably no one among us who does not know this traditional method, that is, in this method, a text or educational material is read, translated, and the necessary part, words, phrases are recorded. This method focuses on learning the rules and phonetics of the language being studied. At the same time, this method is effective for those who want to learn the language from a more classical side, but may not be suitable for those who learn the language from a practical side. This method is suitable for those who want to improve their written translation or those who are engaged in activities related to the theory of language in the future. The good thing about this method is that students who learn this method have a solid foundation, which means they can make grammatically correct sentences. But due to the use of writing only, they may have some difficulties in communicating and freely expressing their thoughts. Therefore, during the use of this method, they can easily achieve a positive result if they work on their listening and speaking skills independently and develop them together.

Learning foreign languages by listening

There is a method in pedagogical practice, which is the method of learning foreign languages through cinema, that is, you watch the first 3 or 5 minutes of your favorite episode with the help of subtitles. When you watch with subtitles, you write down all the unfamiliar words in a separate notebook and find the translation, then you watch that part of the episode again without subtitles, and the third time you watch it with the same actors, parodying them if necessary, in the episode you return the sentences. This method is one of the tried and tested methods. The next method is the "shadowing" method. When translated from English, this word is translated as shadow. In this method, you take any podcast from YouTube by native speakers of the foreign language you are learning and try to repeat every word of it in the shadow method. This method will help you pick up natural vocabulary, speak faster and most importantly improve your pronunciation.

Another way to learn foreign languages is the "immersion" method. In this method, you should create the atmosphere of the language you are learning as much as

possible, that is, you should see and hear movies and music in that language. You need to conduct your communication process in that language.

In addition, the fact that the books you are reading are in the same language will make it easier for you to learn a language, and will contribute to increasing your vocabulary. Learning a new language easily and quickly is related to human memory, which means that when we learn something new, sharing it with people around us helps us remember the information we read.

Modern technologies also have their place in learning foreign languages. As mentioned above, in the process of language learning, we can watch movies, music, cartoons through TV, laptop and smart phones. Today, many people find and read pdf forms of books on the Internet. Dictionaries and similar language learning applications also show the increasing demand for modern techniques in foreign language learning today.

According to some psychologists, learning foreign languages has the ability to change a person's outlook, at least partially. Along with learning the language of a country, people have the opportunity to learn the lifestyle, mentality, culture, and customs of the people of that country.

In language learning, first of all, the learner's age, interest and the amount of time he spends on language learning during the day, the atmosphere created for learning that language, the quality of the textbooks used, the level of language learning different approaches are important. Some students attribute their difficulties in learning a language to the fact that they do not have the opportunity to be in foreign countries where the language is spoken, or to the fact that they do not have friends to communicate with in the same language. In fact, in today's developing technology and Internet era, such excuses are considered inappropriate. People always try to do activities that they like and find interesting and find the strength to do them. If a new language is also learned with strong interest and enthusiasm, the desired goal can be reached so easily and quickly. Many people, on the contrary, take this process as an obligation and, as a result, devote less time to activities that they think are boring. On the contrary, if you try to get information, listen, write, read and speak through your new language in the field or topic you are interested in, you can feel how interesting this process is.

Conclusion. Learning foreign languages is natural for people to face some difficulties. But if people want something and do it sincerely, they will definitely achieve it, and various techniques and methods will help them effectively. Language skills: Communicate, listen, read and write regularly in the language, using effective

methods to help you learn a language by a group of scientists and teachers who have experience in learning foreign languages easily and quickly. it will be easier to learn foreign languages based on their skills.

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